

PROMOTING FORMS OF NAMATAK PLANT MEDICINAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract

From time immemorial, people have used wild plants to treat various ailments. Medicinal plants are promising, valuable plants for Uzbekistan, they are widely used for various purposes and are important as raw materials for the food and pharmaceutical industries and as feed for livestock.

Key words: Folk medicine, medicine, pharmaceuticals, agrotechnics, type, variety, reproduction, product preparation, drying technology, vitamin, flavanoid, tincture, drug

Introduction. Our country has a centuries-old tradition of treating various diseases on the basis of medicinal plants. On the basis of our rich heritage, recommended by our great compatriots Al-Beruni, Al-Khwarizmi, Abu Ali ibn Sinodek for use in ancient medical practice, today the Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Institute of Plant Chemistry, Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute and a number of other universities. Samples of the rich flora of our republic, which are scientifically based and confirmed by clinical trials, have found their place in medical practice today.

Uzbekistan is very rich in flora and includes many species of naturally growing fruit and medicinal plants.

Prospective forms of blessing. Namatak (Rosa) is a medicinal plant widely used in the pharmaceutical industry due to its medicinal properties. The natural populations of this plant in the Republic have a rich gene pool, and their study and selection of promising forms with valuable economic and biological characteristics and their introduction into production is one of the current issues in forestry and medicinal botany. At present, there are more than 500 hectares of namatak plantations in the forestry system, which are planted on the basis of seedlings of random, low-vitamin species due to the lack of localized varieties of namatak and cervitamine forms in the country.

The degree of drought tolerance of namatak can be determined by its ability to retain water in the leaves. The high temperature of the air and the lack of moisture in the soil during the growing season affect the general condition of the bush. The effect of the dry season occurs as follows: the number and size of leaves decreases at the edges of the branches, fruit buds are formed less for the next year, the existing fruits are crushed.

Therefore, it is of practical importance to study the drought and heat resistance of namatak forms. To do this, the leaves are collected from twigs growing in the center of the bush. Moisture loss from the leaves is detected after 2,4,8 and 12 hours, and in the dry season of the form it is possible to determine the adaptive degree of the form according to the amount of total moisture in the leaves. Drought tolerance of plants is closely related to the fact that the leaves are watered. To determine it, the collected leaves are first weighed and then dried in an oven at 105 C until absolutely dry. Water level (%) is determined by the following formula.

Medicinal properties of Fructus rosae (Plodyshipovnika)

“Ranoguldoshlar” - belongs to the family Rosaceae.

Namatak species is a thorny shrub up to 2 m tall. It blooms from May to July, the fruits ripen in August-September. Namatak species grow in forests, along streams, among bushes, on the dry rocky slopes of mountains, and elsewhere. Some species of namatak differ from each other depending on the color, shape, size of the fruit, the thorn on the bark of the rod, and the number and location of the thorns on the rod. The fruits of the plant are harvested from late August (when they turn red) until late autumn. A tarpaulin glove is worn to prevent thorns from getting into the hands while picking the fruit. The product contains vitamins C, V2, K1, R, 12-18 mg% carotene, about 18% sugars, 4-5% additives, about 2% citric and malic acids, 3.7% pectin and other substances. The fruit of the namatak plant contains a mixture of several different vitamins, so its drugs are used in the treatment and prevention of avitaminosis. In folk medicine, namatak has long been used for the prevention and treatment of kidney and urinary tract diseases, hepatitis, gallstones, anemia and others. In addition, the extract of namatak, syrup is fortified in the form of drainage. Namatak oil is made from seeds, which are used to treat stomach ulcers.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it should be noted that meeting the demand for medicinal plants in our country and the supply of medicinal plants is an important and priority task for agricultural workers.

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